

A REVIEW ON SUBSTITUTE PISTON ENGINE COMBUSTION SYSTEM WITH THE HELP OF HOMOGENOUS CHARGE COMPRESSION IGNITION THEORY USING METHYL ALCOHOL AND DIESEL FUEL

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Abstract

In comparison to conventional engines, homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) engine technology is relatively young and has not yet reached a level of maturity that would allow for commercialization. It may leverage both the benefits of both engine configurations—high engine efficiency and low emissions—by using either spark ignition or compression ignition. A large variety of fuels with low emissions can be used in HCCI engines. Owing to these benefits, HCCI engines can be used in hybrid engine configurations, which further reduce fuel usage. However, before the engine can be commercialized, several issues with it, like banging and a low to medium working load range, must be fixed. Consequently, in order to comprehend the behavior of HCCI engines, a thorough investigation must be conducted.

Keywords: engine, efficiency, emission, ignition

Introduction

To improve the quality of the ambient air, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, secure primary energy resources, and meet the ever-tougher emission regulations, the automotive industry must develop clean technologies with reduced fuel usage. As a result, in an era of intense competition, fuel and engines utilized in the transportation industry must meet two significant challenges: increasing efficiency and lowering emissions. Within the automotive industry, two main combustion technologies that are well-established are Compression Ignition (CI) and Spark Ignition (SI). Both CI and SI engines have advantages and disadvantages and run on fossil fuels. The spark discharge that is theoretically provided at the conclusion of the compression stroke ignites this uniform mixture. In spark ignition engines, the timing of the spark discharge controls when combustion begins. Because SI engines have a fixed air/fuel ratio, the only way to regulate engine load is to control the mass flow of air into the combustion

chamber. The throttle employed for this purpose reduces efficiency and causes pumping losses. Because it uses premixed charge with stoichiometric fuel-air ratio ($\lambda=1$), it produces extremely low soot emissions. However, because of pumping loss and a lower compression ratio (usually between 8 and 12), which is limited by knocking, it also has lower thermal efficiency. Therefore, SI engines that have precise air-fuel ratio control and three-way catalytic converters are extremely clean power plants, but their efficiency is restricted due to knocking, throttling, and the lean flammability limits. A conventional CI engine, on the other hand, makes use of a heterogeneous fuel/air mixture. In the suction stroke, only the air is drawn in. And at the end of the compression stroke, theoretically, the fuel is injected quickly and directly into the combustion chamber. After a brief delay, the injected fuel is then automatically ignited. The lengthy processes of droplet formation, collisions, break-up, and evaporation occur between the fuel injection and the beginning of combustion events. The cylinder temperature in a conventional diesel engine is roughly 2700 K. Less pumping loss and increased efficiency are two benefits of the higher compression ratio (usually between 12 and 24). CI engines are incredibly effective power plants, but they are limited by the trade-off between emissions of particulate matter (PM) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). As a result, in order to minimize NO_x emissions and to encourage better fuel-air mixing, which in turn reduces smoke emissions, the maximum cylinder temperature must be kept low. However, because of their exceptional fuel efficiency, CI engines are frequently utilized for both personal and commercial transportation. Significantly contributing to the air pollution in cities are both CI and SI engines. These engines produce emissions of unburned hydrocarbons (UBHC) and carbon monoxide (CO), which contribute to global warming. These engines emit nitrogen oxides and hydrocarbons, which react with the atmosphere to create particulate matter known as photochemical smog. respiratory episodes and asthma are brought on by diesel engines. Worldwide, stricter emission regulations that mandate a simultaneous decrease in PM and NO_x emissions are being implemented due to the detrimental effects of these pollutants on human health. Certain researchers have indicated that by utilizing advanced combustion technologies, it is possible to improve the fuel efficiency of conventional piston engines by up to 25% and reduce harmful emissions almost completely. The next generation of advanced combustion concepts, such as Low Temperature Combustion (LTC), Stratified Charge Compression Ignition (SCCI), and Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI), have the potential to simultaneously reduce PM and NO_x emissions while maintaining high thermal efficiency.

Literature Review

According to Pravin Kumar and A. Rehman, the automotive industry is currently compelled to develop clean technologies with reduced fuel consumption in order to improve ambient air quality, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and ensure energy security. Furthermore, the development of new, highly efficient, and environmentally friendly combustion systems becomes crucial due to the ongoing strict emission regulations and the rapid depletion of primary energy resources. As a result, research in this area is necessary. Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI) technology is one such combustion system that can simultaneously lower particulate matter (PM) and oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) while preserving thermal efficiency comparable to that of traditional diesel engine combustion. But some problems, like controlled auto-ignition, combustion phasing control, , operating range, homogeneous charge preparation, cold start, pressure rise rate, noise, and emissions of carbon

monoxide (CO) and unburned hydro carbon (UHC) must all be resolved before HCCI engines can be used commercially. Stratified Charge Compression Ignition (SCCI) and Low Temperature Combustion (LTC) are two more comparable combustion concepts that can be viewed as an extension of HCCI. This essay examines the benefits and drawbacks of each of the three advanced combustion concepts.

According to Mohammad Izadi Najafabadi and Nuraini Abdul Aziz, engine and vehicle manufacturers are facing consumer and government demands for low emissions and fuel efficiency. Compared to other forms of combustion, homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) is a cleaner and more effective alternative combustion technology. Even though HCCI engines have higher thermal efficiency and NO_x emissions than conventional engines, there are still a number of significant issues with HCCI combustion, including poor cold start capability, limited power output, and timing issues with ignition. This study included a review of the literature on HCCI engines, as well as an investigation of the issues surrounding HCCI and suggested solutions from the perspective of ignition timing, which is the primary issue with these engines.

Assistant Professor P. Venkataramana of the Mechanical Engineering Department at MITS, Madanaoalle, introduces that, Pollution standards have gotten more and more strict in the context of environmental regulations and sustainable development. These days, one of the primary objectives of engine researchers is to design the most environmentally friendly and fuel-efficient internal combustion engine possible in order to meet future emission standards. Combustion using homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) has the potential to be very effective and emit few pollutants. While generating extremely low emissions of particulate matter (PM) and oxides of nitrogen (NO_x), hybrid continuous-fuel injection (HCCI) engines can achieve efficiencies comparable to those of compression-ignition direct-injection (CIDI) engines, an upgraded variant of the widely used diesel engine. Gasoline, diesel, and the majority of alternative fuels can all be used in HCCI engines.

The homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) engine technology is described by Shamla A. Mulane and S. D. Limaye of the Mechanical Engineering Department at the MIT College of Engineering Pune. The development of clean technology in cars with lower fuel consumption and higher efficiency is necessary for improving ambient air quality, reducing greenhouse gas emissions from automobile engines, and ensuring energy security. High compression ratio, lean homogeneous air fuel mixture, complete and instantaneous combustion, which results in homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI), are the factors to be taken into account when designing this kind of technology. The features of Compression Ignition (CI) and Spark-Ignition (SI) are combined in HCCI. Gasoline, diesel, and the majority of alternative fuels can all be used in HCCI engines.

In comparison to conventional engines, homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) engine technology is relatively new and has not yet reached a level of maturity that would allow it to be commercialized, as explained by A.A. Hairuddin, A.P. Wahle, and T. Yusaf. It can leverage both the benefits of both engine configurations—high engine efficiency and low emissions—by using either spark ignition or compression ignition. Owing to these benefits, HCCI engines can be used in hybrid engine configurations, which further reduce fuel consumption. Before the engine can be commercialized, a few issues with HCCI engines, like knocking and a low to medium operating load

range, must be fixed. Consequently, in order to comprehend the behavior of HCCI engines, a thorough investigation must be conducted.

HCCI Principle

When using the HCCI mode of combustion, the fuel and air are combined before the combustion process begins. As a result of the compression stroke's rise in temperature, the mixture spontaneously ignites at several locations throughout the charge volume. The arrangement of the combustion process in this mode leads to extremely lean and diluted mixture conditions during combustion. This lowers the bulk and localized combustion temperatures, which in turn significantly lowers the NO_x emissions. Additionally, the fuel and air are well mixed (homogeneous) in the HCCI mode, in contrast to conventional CI combustion. Therefore, there is a significant decrease in PM generation when there are no rich fuel regions in the combustion chamber. Consequently, the lack of high temperatures in the area and a rich. It is made possible for the simultaneous reduction of NO_x and PM emissions during the combustion process by the fuel-air mixture.

Fig1.Start of combustion

Working of HCCI engine

The four-stroke Otto cycle is the basis for HCCI engines, where fuel delivery control is crucial to managing the combustion process. Fuel injectors installed straight into the cylinder head inject fuel into each cylinder's combustion chamber during the intake stroke. This happens separately from the air induction that happens through the intake plenum. Fuel and air have been completely introduced and mixed in the combustion chamber of the cylinder by the end of the intake stroke.

Heat builds up in the combustion chamber as the piston starts to move back up during the compression stroke. The fuel/air mixture will spontaneously ignite when the piston reaches the end of this stroke due to the accumulation of heat—a spark is not required.

for the power stroke, and press the piston down. The combustion process is a lean, low temperature, flameless release of energy throughout the entire combustion chamber, in contrast to traditional spark engines (and even diesels). In order to produce equivalent power, the entire fuel and air mixture are burned simultaneously, using a lot less fuel and emitting far fewer emissions in the process.

The exhaust valves close early, trapping some of the latent combustion heat, but not all of the exhaust gases can be released before the piston reverses direction once more and starts the exhaust stroke at the end of the power stroke. In order to help control combustion temperatures and emissions,

a small amount of fuel is injected into the combustion chamber for a pre-charge before this heat is maintained.

Fig.2 Differences among SI, CI, and HCCI engines

Table 1. Comparison between conventional SI engine and HCCI engine

Basic of comparison	SI engine	HCCI engine
Efficiency	Less	More
Throttle Losses	More	No
Compression Ratios	Low	High
NOx emission	Comparatively low	Less

Table 2. Comparison between conventional CI engine and HCCI engine

Basics of comparison	CI engine	HCCI engine
Efficiency	High	Equally high
Combustion Temperature	1900-2100k	800-1100k
Cost	Comparatively high	Less
Combustion Duration	More	Less
PM and NOx emission	More	Less

Two stroke HCCI Engine

Fig.3 Ricardo 2/4 sight engine

Fig4. Lotus OMNIVORE two stoke engine

Challenges in HCCI combustion

Despite the fact that HCCI combustion has a number of intrinsic benefits, there are still certain problems that prevent the HCCI engine from being used in commercial engines. The ignition control is the most challenging obstacle. In general, ignition control is more difficult to regulate than direct control mechanisms, which regulate ignition timing in SI and CI engines, respectively, using fuel injectors or spark plugs. The charge mixture's composition and temperature history govern ignition in HCCI mode. The following are listed as the primary difficulties with HCCI combustion:

- 1) The difficulty in combustion phasing control
- 2) High levels of UHC & CO emissions
- 3) Range of operation
- 4) Cold start capacity
- 5) Homogenous mixture preparation
- 6) Abnormal pressure rise with noise
- 7) Prompt response of cycle transient
- 8) Engine control strategies and systems
- 9) Cylinder to cylinder variation

Recent developments in HCCI

The limitations of this technology have been surmounted with great success thanks to recent advancements in HCCI technology. The technology is promising for the upcoming generations because of its broad range of applications and usage in numerous industries. For over 15 years, major automakers like GM, Ford, and Cummins have been investigating the potential of HCCI technology. General Motors has initiated educational initiatives at multiple universities to advance research endeavors in this field. Engineers can now test the performance and efficiency of HCCI engines using various combinations of non-conventional fuels by experimenting with different fuel mixture blends thanks to HCCI.

With redesigned HCCI engines, General Motors has demonstrated the Opel Vectra and Saturn Aura. Mercedes-Benz has created the Dies Otto prototype engine, which features controlled auto ignition. The F-700 concept car featured it at the 2007 Frankfurt Auto Show. Two engine types are

being developed by Volkswagen for HCCI operation. The first, known as the Combined Combustion System, or CCS, is based on a 2.0-liter diesel engine from the VW Group but injects fuel homogeneously rather than using traditional diesel injection. When the car goes into production, General Motors will offer the 2.2-liter HCCI engine-equipped Vauxhall Insignia prototype alongside their eco FLEX range of small-capacity, turbocharged petrol and diesel engines. Auto Express was granted access to the vehicle prototype in May 2008. Although official numbers are unavailable, fuel efficiency is anticipated to be roughly 43 mpg (miles per gallon) with carbon dioxide emissions of roughly 150 grammes per kilometer. This is an improvement over the current 2.2-liter petrol engine's 37 mpg and 180 grammes per kilometer. When cruising or operating at low speeds, the new engine runs in HCCI mode; when the throttle is opened, it switches to conventional spark-ignition.

Advantages of HCCI

- Science HCCI engines are fuel-lean; they can operate at diesel like compression ratios, thus achieving 30% higher efficiencies than conventional SI gasoline engine.
- Homogeneous mixing of fuel and air leads to cleaner combustion and lower emissions. Because peak temperatures are significantly lower than in typical SI engines, NO_x levels are almost negligible. Additionally, the technique does not produce soot.
- HCCI engines can operate on gasoline, diesel fuel, and almost alternative fuels.
- HCCI avoids throttle losses, which further improves efficiency.

Disadvantages of HCCI

- Achieving cold start capability.
- High heat release and pressure rise rates contribute to engine wear.
- Autoignition is difficult to control, unlike the ignition event in SI and diesel engines, which are controlled by spark plug and in cylinder fuel injectors, respectively.
- HCCI engines have a small power range, constrained at low loads by lean flammability limits and high loads by in cylinder pressure restriction.

Conclusion

For light-duty vehicles, an efficient gasoline-powered HCCI engine is a significant advancement over SI engines. The HCCI combustion engines exhibit the capability to concurrently decrease NO_x and PM emissions, all the while preserving a thermal efficiency that is comparable to that of a traditional diesel engine. Furthermore, because HCCI engines would probably use lower-pressure fuel injection equipment and because of their potential for using emission control devices that rely less on costly and scarce precious metals, HCCI engines would probably be less expensive than CI engines. However, there are certain difficulties with HCCI combustion, like high noise levels, high rate of pressure rise, misfiring at low and knocking at high loads, cold start issues, and difficulty with homogenous mixture preparation. high HC and CO combustion levels, etc. The two primary problems with HCCI combustion are the preparation of the homogeneous mixture and auto-ignition control. To regulate the phasing of HCCI combustion, two essentially distinct methods are feasible: Modifying the propensity of the mixture to self-ignition. Modifying the temperature history of the mixture over time. A combustion concept called HCCI was created in response to the requirement for reduced NO_x and PM emissions as well as increased efficiency. It needs a great deal of improvement but can effectively solve every issue. There is currently no workable solution for the

production-related combustion control issue.

References

- [1] P.Venkatrama (2013), Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI) Engine, International Journal of Engineering Research And Technology (IJERT) ISSN:2278-0181 Vol.2 Issue 2, February-2013
- [2] P.V.Ramana, D Maheshwar, B. Unmeneshwar Gowd (2015), Review on Research and development of HCCI technology, International Journal of IT, Engineering And Applied Sciences Research (IJIEASR) Volume 4, No.5, May 2015
- [3] Jack Hunicz, Pawel Krzaczek (2016), Detailed Speciation of Emissions from Low-Temperature Combustion in a Gasoline HCCI Engine, Poland Journal Environmental Studies Volume 25 No.1 (2016), 137-145
- [4] Anku kumar singh, M.K. Paswan (2014), Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition Engine, International Journal Of Mechanical Engineering And Robotics Research (IJMERR) ISSN 2278-0149 Vol.3, No.1, January 2014
- [5] Krzysztof Motyl, Tadeusz J. Rychter (2003), HCCI Engine – A Preliminary Analysis Journal of KONES Internal Combustion Engines 2003, Vol. 10, 3-4
- [6] Pravin Kumar, A.Rehman Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition (HCCI) Combustion Engine- A Review IOSR Journal of Mechanical And Civil Engineering e-ISSN:2278-1648, p-ISSN: 2320-334X, Volume 11, Issue 6, Ver.II (Nov.- Dec. 2014), PP 47-6
- [7] N. Kaahaaina, Aaron J. Simon, P. A. Caton, Ch. Edwards: "Use of Dynamic Valving to Achieve Residual-Affected Combustion", SAE 2001-01-0549 (2001)
- [8] D. Law, J. Allen, D. Kemp, G. Kirkpatrick, T. Copland: "Controlled Combustion in an IC-Engine with a Fully Variable Train", SAE 2000-01-0251 (2000)
- [9] G. Kontarakis, Tom H. Ma: "Demonstration of HCCI Using a Single Cylinder FourStroke SI Engine with Modified Valve Timing", SAE 2000-01-2870 (2000)
- [10] J. Willand, R.G. Nieberding, G. Vent, Ch. Enderle: "The Knocking Syndrome: its Cure and Potential", SAE 982483 (1998)
- [11] K. Hiraya, K. Hasegawa, T. Urushihara, A. Liyama, T. Ltoh: "A study of Gasoline Fueling Compression Ignition Engine", JSAE 20025006 (2002)
- [12] T. Ma et al: "Method of Operating an Internal Combustion Engine", International Patent Application, WO 01/112333
- [13] J. Dec: "A Computational Study of the Effect of Low Fuel Loading and EGR on Heat Release Rates and Combustion Limits in HCCI Engines", SAE 2002-01-1309 (2002)
- [14] S. Yamamoto, T. Satou, M. Ikuta: "Feasibility Study of Two-Stage Hybrid Combustion in Gasoline Direct Injection Engines", SAE 2002-01-0113 (2002).
- [15] M. Christensen, B. Johansson, P. Amneus, F. Mauss: "Supercharged Homogeneous Charge Compression Ignition" SAE 980787
- [16] A. Higashino, H. Sasaki, K. Kishishita, S. Sekiyama, H. Kawamura: "Compression Ignition Combustion in a Prechambered and Heat Insulated Engine Using a Homogeneous Natural Gas Mixture" SAE 2000-01-0330

- [17] S. Kimura, O. Aoki, H. Ogawa, S. Muranaka: "New Combustion Concept for UltraClean and High-Efficiency Small DI Diesel Engines" SAE 1999-01-3681 (1999)
- [18] Y. Ishibashi, M. Asai: "Improving the Exhaust Emissions of Two Stroke Engines by Applying the Activated Radical Combustion" SAE 960742.